

Enhancing Colorectal Cancer Classification using Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator Algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Deep learning has revolutionized medical image analysis by enabling automated feature extraction and classification with high accuracy. Its ability to learn hierarchical representations makes it a powerful tool for disease diagnosis and plays a crucial role in medical imaging. Hyperparameter optimization (HPO) is the process of selecting the best set of hyperparameters to improve a model's performance in machine learning. Efficient HPO techniques enhance accuracy, convergence speed, and generalization while reducing computational costs. This study explores the impact of HPO on colorectal cancer classification using the CRC-VAL-HE-7K dataset, which consists of 7,180 histology images categorized into nine tissue types. In our experimental pipeline, ResNet-18 is employed for classification, leveraging data preprocessing techniques such as image resizing, normalization, and augmentation. Various HPO methods, including random search, grid search, Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE), and our modified TPE are implemented. The model is evaluated based on accuracy, recall, precision and F1-score. Comparative analysis demonstrates that the modified TPE having 88.85% accuracy enhances the optimization efficiency and classification performance. This research contributes to the advancement of AI-driven automated colorectal cancer classification.

KEYWORDS: *Bayesian optimization, colorectal cancer, deep learning, hyperparameter optimization, ResNet-18, Tree-structured Parzen Estimator.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a major global health concern, ranking as the third most common cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality worldwide (Siegel et al., 2025). Early and accurate diagnosis of CRC is crucial for improving patient outcomes. However, manual histopathological analysis is time-consuming, subject to inter-observer variability, and requires expert pathologists (Zhou et al., 2022). In recent years, deep learning techniques have demonstrated remarkable success in medical image analysis, providing automated solutions for histopathological image classification and improving diagnostic accuracy (Litjens et al., 2017).

Despite the success of deep learning models, their performance heavily depends on hyperparameter optimization (HPO), which involves selecting the best combination of hyperparameters to maximize accuracy, convergence speed, and generalization (Bergstra et al., 2011). Unlike model parameters, which are learned during training, hyperparameters must be predefined, and their selection significantly impacts the model's effectiveness (Zhou et al., 2022).

Several HPO techniques exist, including grid search (Liashchynskiy et al., 2019; Belete et al., 2021; Ogunsanya et al., 2023), random search (Bergstra et al., 2012), and Bayesian optimization-based approaches such as the Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) (Islam et al., 2024; Watanabe et al., 2023; Ozaki et al., 2022). While TPE has been widely used for deep learning hyperparameter tuning, its conventional implementation suffers from uneven search space exploration, limiting its effectiveness.

This study proposes a modified TPE algorithm that enhances search space exploration, ensuring a more uniform distribution of hyperparameter values. The contributions of this research are as follows:

- Modification of the existing TPE algorithm to improve search space coverage, leading to better hyperparameter selection.
- Comparative analysis of multiple HPO methods—grid search, random search, traditional TPE, and modified TPE—evaluating their performance based on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

By optimizing deep learning models for colorectal cancer classification, this study contributes to the advancement of AI-driven medical diagnostics, providing more efficient and reliable automated histopathological image analysis.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

Deep learning has revolutionized medical image classification, enabling accurate disease detection through neural networks like CNNs. Various studies highlight its success in diagnosing conditions like colorectal cancer (Azar et al., 2023 ; Al-Shawesh et al., 2021). However, optimizing hyperparameters is crucial for enhancing model performance. Traditional methods like manual tuning and grid search (Liashchynskiy et al., 2019) ; Belete et al., 2021 ; Ogunsanya et al., 2023), random search (Bergstra et al., 2012) are inefficient, leading to the adoption of advanced techniques such as Bayesian optimization (Watanabe et al., 2023; Ozaki et al., 2022; Rani et al., 2023; Islam et al.,2024), evolutionary algorithms (Vincent et al., 2023), and reinforcement learning (Alrebdi et al., 2022), which enable automated and adaptive parameter selection for improved accuracy and efficiency of CNN models. These approaches not only automate the optimization process but also adapt dynamically to complex datasets, reducing computational overhead and accelerating convergence speed.

3 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

This study presents a systematic approach to improving colorectal cancer classification using deep learning. The methodology encompasses dataset preprocessing, model selection, hyperparameter optimization, training, evaluation, and comparative analysis.

We utilize the CRC-VAL-HE-7K dataset (Azar et al., 2023; Al-Shawesh et al., 2021), comprising histopathological images categorized into nine tissue classes. To enhance model generalization and mitigate class imbalances, preprocessing steps such as image resizing, pixel normalization, and data augmentation (including rotation, flipping, and contrast adjustment) are applied (Zhou et al., 2022). The dataset is split into 80% training, 10% validation, and 10% testing to ensure unbiased performance evaluation.

For classification, we employ ResNet-18, chosen for its efficient feature extraction capabilities and skip connections that mitigate the vanishing gradient problem. The model is trained using the CrossEntropyLoss function and the Adam optimizer. Performance is assessed using key evaluation metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

3.1 Hyperparameter Optimization Using Modified TPE

Hyperparameter tuning is performed to enhance model performance and training efficiency. The Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (TPE), a Bayesian optimization method, is used for this purpose. Traditional TPE models the objective function as two separate probability densities—one for promising hyperparameter values and another for less promising values—guiding the search towards optimal

configurations. However, classical TPE suffers from uneven search space exploration, especially in high-dimensional settings, leading to suboptimal convergence.

To address this limitation, we propose a modified TPE algorithm that improves search space exploration by replacing the random sampling step with Sobol sequence-based quasi-random sampling. The Sobol sequence generates more evenly distributed samples in the search space, reducing clustering in specific regions and ensuring a more uniform exploration of hyperparameter configurations. This modification allows the optimization process to converge faster and find better-performing hyperparameter sets.

A comparative analysis is conducted between grid search (Liashchynskiy et al., 2019; Belete et al., 2021; Ogunsanya et al., 2023), random search (Bergstra et al., 2012), traditional TPE, and the proposed modified TPE method. The evaluation is based on accuracy, convergence speed, and computational efficiency. Experimental results demonstrate that the modified TPE algorithm outperforms other methods, confirming its effectiveness in optimizing deep learning models for AI-driven colorectal cancer diagnostics.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section provides a detailed analysis of the performance of different hyperparameter optimization techniques for colorectal cancer (CRC) classification. The evaluation includes performance comparisons, convergence analysis, computational efficiency, and insights drawn from the findings. The CRC-VAL-HE-7K dataset (Azar et al., 2023; Al-Shawesh et al., 2021) consists of 7,180 hematoxylin and eosin (H&E)-stained histology images from 50 colorectal adenocarcinoma patients, categorized into nine distinct tissue types representing both normal and malignant regions. To enhance model generalization, the dataset undergoes preprocessing steps such as image resizing, pixel normalization, and data augmentation (rotation, flipping, and contrast adjustment) (Zhou et al., 2022) and is split into 80% training, 10% validation, and 10% testing. All experiments were conducted in a Kaggle cloud-based environment using an NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPU for accelerated computations. The implementation was carried out using Python 3.8, with PyTorch 1.12 and Torchvision 0.13 for image preprocessing and model loading. Additional libraries such as NumPy, Pandas, and scikit-learn were utilized for data handling and performance evaluation.

4.1 Performance Comparison of Various HPO Techniques

To assess the impact of hyperparameter tuning, we compare the performance of four methods i.e. random search, grid search, TPE, and modified TPE. The Table 1 summarizes the results as follows:

Table 1. Performance Comparison of Various Hyperparameters Optimization Techniques.

HPO Method	Loss	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Random search	0.64	77.57	0.78	0.70	0.72
Grid search	0.67	75.09	0.71	0.65	0.67
TPE	0.33	87.60	0.88	0.81	0.84
Modified-TPE	0.31	88.85	0.89	0.83	0.87

4.2 Optimal Hyperparameters Obtained by the Proposed Model

Through HPO using Bayesian optimization (Watanabe et al., 2023 ; Ozaki et al., 2022) (TPE) and modified TPE, the optimal hyperparameters for the proposed method on the CRC-VAL-HE-7K dataset were identified. Table 2 summarizes the best hyperparameters found by the proposed model as follows.

Table 2. Optimal Hyperparameters Obtained for Various HPO Techniques.

HPO Technique	Batch Size	Learning Rate	Weight Decay
Random search	32	0.000141	1.190
Grid search	128	0.001	0.001
TPE	64	0.000161	0.00088
Modified-TPE	94	0.000111	0.000657

4.3 Convergence Analysis and Observations

Convergence speed is a critical factor in hyperparameter optimization, impacting both computational efficiency and model performance. Traditional methods like grid search and random search require extensive evaluations, leading to slow convergence and high computational costs (Liashchynskiy et al., 2019; Bergstra et al., 2012). In contrast, Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) improves convergence by selecting hyperparameters probabilistically based on a surrogate model, making it more efficient (Watanabe et al., 2023; Ozaki et al., 2022). Our proposed modified TPE further optimizes the search space by refining the initial sampling strategy, resulting in faster convergence and better accuracy for colorectal cancer classification. The experimental results confirm that TPE outperforms traditional methods, while the modified TPE achieves superior accuracy and computational efficiency, making it an effective approach for medical image analysis.

4.4 Comparative Study

In our study, we achieved an accuracy of 88.85% using the modified TPE method incorporating hyperparameter optimization in colorectal cancer classification. This performance surpasses several existing studies employing different methodologies and is shown below in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3. Comparative Analysis Against the Existing Work.

Sl. No.	Author's Name	Methodology Used	Accuracy (%)
1.	Zhou et al. 2022	HCCANet	87.3%
2.	Anggreani et al. 2024	Grid search, Decision tree algorithm	81%
3.	Rani et al. 2023	Bayesian Optimization, Random Forest	86.87%
4.	Proposed Work	ResNet-18, modified TPE	88.85%

These comparisons highlight the effectiveness of our modified TPE approach in enhancing classification performance of colorectal cancer detection.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed study demonstrates effectiveness of the modified TPE algorithm for hyperparameter optimization in colorectal cancer classification using ResNet-18 architecture. The results showed that modified TPE outperformed grid search and random search, achieving competitive results with standard TPE while requiring fewer evaluations and reduced training time. Future research directions include hybrid strategies combining TPE with genetic algorithms or reinforcement learning, as well as parallelization and GPU acceleration, to enhance the scalability and efficiency of TPE for large-scale deep learning applications, ultimately advancing AI-driven diagnostics for automated cancer classification.

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